

Assessing the Effect of Exchange Rate Misalignment on Trade Balance in West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU)

Évaluation de l'effet du désalignement du taux de change sur la Balance Commerciale dans l'Union Economique et Monétaire Ouest Africaine (UEMOA)

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Abstract

This paper used a panel dataset from 1996 to 2021 to examine the effect of exchange rate misalignment on trade balance in West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU). The paper applied Pooled Mean Group Estimator Model and Panel Causality. The variables used were trade balance (TB), real exchange rate misalignment (RERM), trade openness (OPN), foreign direct investment (FDI), interest rate (INT) and inflation rate (INF). The findings indicate that in the long run, RERM, FDI, and INF exert a significant negative impact on trade balance, while OPN demonstrates a significant positive influence. Furthermore, in the short run trade openness has a significant positive effect on trade balance while Interest rate has a significant negative effect. In line with these findings, this study recommends among other, WAEMU countries should enhance the quality and innovation of exports by processing raw materials and exploring new markets to maintain a trade surplus. Also, to mitigate the negative impact of FDI on TB, governments should enhance domestic investment and FDI towards the industrial sector. Finally, the BCEAO should control WAEMU's currency management, possibly detaching it from the euro to stabilize the trade balance.

Keywords: trade balance; exchange rate misalignment; WAEMU's countries; overvaluation; undervaluation.

Résumé

Cet article examine l'effet du désalignement du taux de change sur la Balance commerciale en utilisant les données de panel de 1996 à 2021 dans l'Union Economique et Monétaire Ouest Africaine. Pooled Mean Group Estimator Model et Panel Causality test sont utilisés comme méthodes. Les variables utilisées sont la Balance Commerciale (BC), le désalignement du taux de change réel (DTCR), l'ouverture commerciale (OV), l'Investissement Direct étranger (IDE), le Taux d'intérêt (INT) et le Taux d'inflation (INF). Les résultats indiquent qu'à long terme le DTCR, l'IDE et l'INF impactent négativement et significativement la balance Commerciale pendant que l'Ouverture exerce une influence positivement significative. Mais à court terme, l'Ouverture a un effet positif sur la Balance commerciale alors que le Taux d'intérêt exerce un effet significativement négatif. Ainsi, l'article recommande entre autres, à l'Union d'améliorer ses exportations en transformant ses matières premières et en explorant de nouveaux marchés afin de maintenir le surplus de son solde commercial. Aussi, pour réduire l'impact négatif des IDE, les pays devraient orienter leurs Investissements domestiques et étrangers vers l'industrialisation. En fin, la Banque centrale de l'Union devrait soigneusement gérer sa monnaie, la détacher si possible de l'euro afin de stabiliser la balance commerciale.

Mots clés : Balance commerciale ; désalignement du taux de change ; pays de l'UEMOA ; surévaluation et sous-évaluation.

Introduction

From 1996 to 2020, the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) recorded a persistent deficit in its trade balance (BCEAO, 2020). This is the consequence of several constraints which exert pressure on the structural transformation of the union members' economies. The BCEAO report of 2020 on WAEMU zone reveals that its exports are essentially composed of raw materials dominated by gold (31.8%), cocoa (16.8%), oil (6.8%), cotton (4.8%) and cashew (3.9%). The annual average increase in exports was 6.84% for the period of the study. The imports are mainly composed of products such as oil, current consumption products, intermediate products, and equipment. These imports are increasing at a rate of 7.72% compared to that of exports. This suggests a deficit trade balance throughout the period under review. The deficit trade experiencing an upward trend as indicated in the Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 : Imports, Exports and trade balance trend for the period 1996-2020¹

Source: constructed by the authors based on BCEAO's data of 2021.

In addition to this, since the creation of franc Cfa, the exchange rate policies in this union were led by the French authorities and operate in an environment of fixed exchange rates. These constraints limit the capacity of WAEMU's countries to offer services and goods having a high-value addition. These include the narrowness of the domestic market, the low diversification of production, the low level of physical and human capital and the high exposure to external shocks among other. Gnansounou and Verdier-Chouchrane, (2012) in Couharde et al. (2013) add also that the peg of franc Cfa to the euro as a potential source of misalignment. In this understanding, it can be observed

¹ The data on the Imports are in negative values, because it constitutes an outflow in terms of money while Exports constitute an inflow.

that, when the euro becomes strong/weak, the CFA franc follows the same trend independently of the fundamentals of the economy that determine the real equilibrium exchange rate. This situation creates an over or under-valuation which affects directly the trade balance through export and import prices (Mussa, 1984; Dornbusch, 1996; Yeshineh, 2017).

Currency is misaligned when its value digresses away from its equilibrium level (Aguirre & Calderón, 2005; Jongwanich, 2009). The magnitude or the level of the misalignment is the difference between the observed Real Exchange Rate (RER) and a (non-observed) “equilibrium” RER. An “overvalued” RER indicates that the value of the current RER is above its equilibrium value, with an “undervalued” RER indicating the opposite. Since the equilibrium exchange rate (EER) allows for an economy to reach its internal and external equilibriums, exchange rate misalignment impacts not only a competitiveness of an economic but also an indicator of the viability of a monetary union (Coulibaly & Gnimassoun, 2012). Obviously, as noted by Cottani et al. (1990), any change in the real exchange rate that may reflects the external and or internal shocks that change the equilibrium real exchange rate (ERER) is consider as misalignment. The mismatches of the currencies are used as instruments to predict future exchange rate shifts among floaters and to assess the need to adjust the exchange rate among countries with less flexible regimes. It has been documented that persistent overvaluations constitute a signal of possible currency crashes (Krugman, 1979; Frankel & Rose, 1996; Kaminsky & Reinhart, 1999) and they also have led to a drastic adjustment of relative prices and to a decline in the aggregate growth rate of the economy. On the other hand, real exchange rate movements determine production and consumption choices between domestic and international goods and policymakers remark that RER is an additional tool throughout an economy can be influenced. It’s why some countries tried to maintain their currencies undervalued in order to boost the performance of the export sector and, hence, aggregate economic activity. Conversely, an overvaluation affects negatively the competitiveness of an economy by increasing imports and decreasing exports.

In below, figure 2 presents the graphs of Real exchange rate misalignment of the WAEMU zone, generated from the Hodrick Prescott Filter (HP).

Figure 2: Graphs of REER_EREER_RERM (MIS)

Source: the authors, 2024

The supposed relationship between exchange rate misalignment begs the question as to whether exchange rate misalignment affects trade balance in WAEMU's countries. In other words, to what extent does exchange rate misalignment influence trade balance in WAEMU countries?

Several empirical studies have been conducted on this issue and their findings are inconclusive. Indeed, studies like Mamun et al. (2021), Rikhotso and Bonga-Bonga (2021), Nicita (2013), Jongwanich (2009), Mohamad et al. (2009), among other, align with the theoretical expectation of a negative impact of exchange rate misalignment on trade balance. Conversely, findings from Zhang and MacDonald (2013), Umaru and Odjegba (2013), Fisera and Horvath (2022), Elfathaoui (2018), Diop et al. (2018), Sekkat and Varoudakis (2000) among other, present a mixture of results. Particularly, for the West African Economy and Monetary Union, there is dearth of empirical evidence on the effect of exchange rate misalignment on trade balance. In the set of papers reviewed, only Diop et al. (2018), Naze (2018), Sekkat and Varoudakis (2000), and Keho (2021) among other, have slightly addressed the topic and their conclusions are far from unanimous.

The aforementioned papers addressed some aspects of this paper on the relationship between exchange rate misalignment and trade balance. However, this paper is different from the previous studies at least in one way. This paper to the best of our knowledge is the first that investigates using panel analysis the relationship between exchange rate misalignment and trade balance in WAEMU's countries. Therefore, this paper has addressed part of the gap in the literature by investigating the causal links between the variables of interest. Thus, the main objective of this

paper is to assess the effect of exchange rate misalignment on trade balance in WAEMU's countries.

This paper is organized as follows. After this introduction, the first section presents a review of literature while the second one presents the methodology used. Results and discussions are addressed in the third section. Conclusion is rendered at the end.

1. Literature Review

This section is presented in two sub-sections i.e., theoretical framework and review of empirical literature.

1.1. Theoretical Framework

The literature provides four main approaches to identify and analyze the trade balance determinants. Sure, we have various perspectives in economics, including the elasticity approach, absorption approach, monetary approach, and the twin deficit hypothesis (see Yeshineh, 2017 for deep understanding). One of the most popular theoretical ways used to explore the link between exchange rate and by extension exchange rate misalignment and trade balance is the elasticity approach. This type of analysis was first presented by Marshall (1923), then further developed by Lerner (1944), Robinson (1947), and Machlup (1955). According to this method, the trade balance or balance of payments is determined by the elasticity of demand for imports by citizens of the country and exports by outsiders. It is worried about how shifts in the relative costs of domestic and imported commodities may affect the trade balance. So, a change in the exchange rate will change the domestic currency price of foreign goods. Therefore, currency devaluation (depreciation) affects a country's trade balance through changes in the relative prices of goods and services internationally (Yeshineh, 2017). A country can devalue its currency under a fixed exchange rate regime or allow it to depreciate naturally in the open market to reduce its relative prices in order to reduce trade deficit. In this approach, the outcome of currency depreciation (devaluation) centers on how responsive the demand is for a country's imports and exports in relation to price changes. When demand or supply is elastic, it means that quantity demanded or supplied will be relatively responsive to the change in price. An inelastic demand or supply indicates that quantity is relatively unresponsive to price changes. This operates on the so-called Marshal-Lerner condition, which states that:

- i. devaluation will enhance the trade balance if the combined absolute value of the foreign elasticity of demand for exports and the home country's elasticity of demand for imports surpasses one ($|\eta_x| + |\eta_m| > 1$).
- ii. If the sum of the demand elasticities is less than one ($|\eta_x| + |\eta_m| < 1$), then devaluation will deteriorate the trade balance.
- iii. If $(|\eta_x| + |\eta_m|) = 1$, then devaluation (depreciation) will neither improve nor worsen the current account (trade balance).

1.2. Review of Empirical Literature

Researches on how currency misalignment affects trade balance are relatively scarce and are especially hard to find for our target area of WAEMU. Most studies addressing the question of misalignment examine its influence on economic performance and concern in majority ASEAN-Emerging countries. The few studies identified and reviewed are presented below. Furthermore, results from these studies are divergent and inconclusive.

In 2021, in their paper, Mamun et al. aim to analyze how currency misalignment affects trade balance of 21 emerging market economies (EMEs) from 1980 to 2016. Initially, they use a single equation approach to examine this relationship separately. Subsequently, they incorporate these findings into a trade regression model alongside undervaluation and overvaluation, employing the system generalized method of moment estimation approach to understand the dynamic interplay between the trade balance and real exchange rate misalignment. According to the study's findings, greater real exchange rate misalignment, which is a composite of undervaluation and overvaluation, contributes to the improvement of trade imbalances. Additionally, they discover as expected by the theory that the trade balance is positively impacted by undervaluation and unfavorably by overvaluation. These conclusions have been supported by the results of Rikhotso and Bonga-Bonga in 2021 for approximately the same area and the same period. Indeed, looking at the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), which are also major EMEs—they discovered evidence of an asymmetric relationship between the two variables. The study examined the relationship between RER misalignment and trade balance for the 1990–2016 period. As to the study, the trade balance of the BRICS countries experienced an improvement when their currencies were undervalued, but it declined when they were overvalued. Nicita (2013), has interested to the extent to which exchange rate affects international trade and trade policy. His methodology consists of assessing fixed effects models on a comprehensive panel dataset encompassing about 100

nations and covering 10 years (2000-2009). The findings of his paper are generally in line with those of the recent literature supporting the importance of mismatch of exchange rate. In more detail, the results specify that exchange rate misalignments do affect international trade flows in a substantial manner. Currency undervaluation is found to promote exports and restrict imports, while the converse holds in the case of overvaluation. So, this results through exports and imports effects, mean that misalignment of exchange rate affects negatively trade balance of these countries in the period of the study. In the same vein, using panel data analysis by applying a fixed effect model on export equations both at the aggregate and sectorial levels, Mohamad et al. (2009) in the case of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand economies from 1970 to 1998, found that the RER misalignment is found to be negatively and significantly associated with export. This implies that a lower (more depreciated) equilibrium real exchange rate can enhance export performance. So according to these conclusions, if we assume that a change in exports, will impact trade balance, one can say these authors have empirically found that the RER misalignment impacts negatively trade balance in their areas of their study. Furthermore, Jongwanich (2009) has examined the impact of RER misalignment on export performance by using the method of Johansen (1988), on eight Asian countries² during the period 1995–2008. The author found a negative relationship between RER misalignment and export volume in almost all countries. For this author, this negative relationship implies that RER misalignment could adversely affect export performance therefore, trade balance of these countries adversely affected by misalignment of exchange rate on the study period. The same conclusion has been found by Pick and Vollrath (1994) in 4 of the 10 developing countries. Indeed, these authors used specifically a misalignment index in analyzing its effect on export performance (even though not on trade balance). The empirical estimations by using an appropriate panel data regression, showed that exchange rate misalignment had a statistically significant negative impact on agricultural export performance and by extension on trade balance. The case of single country has been also addressed and some of the conclusions corroborate the findings above. For instance, Fuat (1998), examines the effects of Turkey's currency rate mismatch. He discovered a strong inverse link between misalignment and trade balance, as the theory predicted. To put it another way, the trade balance responds to changes in the equilibrium RER,

² These countries are: People Republic of China, Hong Kong (China), India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand.

indicating that exchange rate management may be able to keep trade balance in a reasonable range. Practically, Fuat observed that the misalignment had a net negative effect on the trade balance of about -0.38, meaning that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% rise in misalignment may result in a 0.38% decline in the trade balance of Turkey. Approximately the findings of Rajan et al. (2004) are not far from these conclusions. In fact, these authors examine in some detail, bilateral real equilibrium exchange rates of the Thai baht against the Japanese yen over two decades (Q1: 1981 to Q3: 1999) by using the unrestricted vector autoregressive (VAR). Their results show that the misalignment in the bilateral real exchange rate against the Japanese yen is consistent with a significant widening of Thailand's trade deficits between 1990 and 1996 just prior to the crisis in 1997. In other words, it means that Thailand currency (Thai baht) misalignment increases imports and decreases exports of the concern country, therefore deteriorate its trade balance. To close this part, the works of Ebaidalla (2014) and Njindan (2016) can be also mentioned. Ebaidalla in the case of Sudan, is interested by the behavior of real exchange rate misalignment and equilibrium exchange rate from 1979 to 2009. Additionally, the effect of misaligning actual exchange rates on the performance of the economy is investigated. Proving the long-run analysis, it's interesting to note that the misalignment coefficient sign is negative and significant. The results of this study suggest that misalignment of exchange rates negatively affects exports performance under the period of the study. This is in line with the majority of earlier researches, including studies by Nabli and Venganzones-Varoudakis (2002) and Elbadawi et al. (2012), which show that overvaluation of the exchange rate has harmed Sudan's export output. Njindan (2016) assessed the effect of exchange rate undervaluation on sectoral performance in South Africa using annual dataset from 1962 to 2016 and applying Ordinary Least Squares regression and, the Generalized Method of Moment (GMM) for the estimation. The findings from both techniques clarify a significant positive relationship between exchange rate undervaluation and industrial output in the study area.

If in the above evidence, rate of exchange misalignment – overvaluation- harms trade balance by decreasing exports and increasing imports and inversely undervaluation, some little studies find mixed results. In this sense, Zhang and MacDonald in 2013, in their paper estimate equilibrium exchange rates for 23 OECD countries and four less mature economies in a panel data set. These estimations were then used to investigate currency misalignments for the sample of countries over the period 1980 to 2011 using the long-term association between real exchange rate and trade balance. One interesting aspect of the results is that not all of the implied misalignments accord

with what would be generally accepted as the stylized facts for certain currencies. It means that this finding support adversely the idea that overvaluation can affects negatively or do not affect trade balance in the concern sample. This kind of mitigate result has also evidenced by Fisera and Horvath (2021) for 11 new member states of the European Union. Indeed, using heterogeneous panel cointegration methods, they evaluated the impact of exchange rate misalignments on the balance of trade and the role that participation in global value chains plays in this effect. They discovered asymmetric effects of real currency misalignments: undervaluation has no significant effect on the trade balance, while overvaluation has a moderately negative impact. These conclusions seem to be supported by Grobar (1993) on 10 middle-income countries (Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Greece, Malaysia, Mexico, Philippines, South Africa, Thailand and Yugoslavia). Grobar focuses on 10 middle-income countries. She considers the role of misalignment as measured by the black-market premium. The results show that Misalignment seems, not to have played a central role in determining exports for the 10 countries. Similarly, Iyke and Ho (2018) in retesting the J-curve, which was conducted using quarterly data for South Africa and her major trading partners, China, Germany, India, Japan, the UK, and the USA, discovered that, under relaxed conditions, the linear specification only supported the J-curve phenomena in two cases – Canada and the USA. However, in every instance, the J-curve phenomena was validated by the nonlinear specification. The case of Nigeria and Marocco had been addressed respectively by Umoru and Odjegba (2013), Ibrahim (2016) and Elfathaoui (2018). In their study, Umoru and Odjegba (2013), analyze the association among rate of exchange misalignment and balance of payments (BOP) mal-adjustment in Nigeria over the sample period of 1973 through 2012 using the vector error correction modelling technique. The most relevant finding of the study is the fact that exchange rate misalignment has shown a positive impact on the Nigerian's balance of payments position, which contradicts the theoretical assumptions, if we consider trade balance is a part important of balance of payment. In order to ascertain the impact of exchange rate misalignment on trade flows in Nigeria for the years 1960 to 2013, Ibrahim (2016) employed a single equation co-integration approach. He found that, on average, Nigeria's real effective exchange rate appreciated between 1960 and 1985 and depreciated between 1986 and 2013. The study's findings also show that, while real exchange rate misalignment has no discernible effect on the number of exports, it does have a significant negative impact on imports and the country's trade balance. Elfathaoui (2018), examines the effects of the real exchange rate (REER) misalignment on the

balance of payments value for the period covering 37 years for Morocco. The results thus obtained show that the effect of the misalignment on the economy through the balance of payments is not confirmed as long as it remains under control, but the effect remains undeniable judging by the structure of the correlation.

Documented experiences of WAEMU include Diop et al. (2018) who examine the impact of real exchange rate misalignments on the performance of the manufacturing sector in Senegal from 1980 to 2015. They estimate equations that explain the changes in manufacturing production by using the indicators of manufacturing value added per capita or per sector employee as explanatory variables. They used the autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) by Pesaran et al. (2001) as their technique of analysis. Their findings show that less undervaluation or more overvaluation have a negative impact on performance and that this impact seems to be linear. Furthermore, Naze (2018) investigates the impact of exchange rate on trade competitiveness in the CFA³ zone and considers the misalignment between REER and EREER. The result appears that being anchored to a foreign currency, CFA franc likely has not helped the CFA countries improve their trade competitiveness. Sekkat and Varoudakis (2000) used three indicators – RER changes, RER volatility, and RER misalignment to examine how exchange rate policies have an impact on manufactured export performance on a panel of major Sub-Saharan African countries for the 1970–1992 period and suggested that exchange rate management significantly determines their export performance. In particular, the study found an indirect relationship between RER misalignment and manufactured exports. However, they argue that manufactured exports are more responsive (positively) to a decrease in misalignment than a real depreciation. Keho is also interested of WAEMU case. In 2021, he looks at the factors influencing trade balance in the context of the nations that make up the West African Economic and Monetary Union between 1975 and 2017. He does this by using the grouped mean version of FMOLS and DOLS in addition to the MGE. The results imply that RER depreciation eventually leads to an improvement in the trade balance. However, the data contradict the J-curve phenomenon, which indicates a short-term deterioration in the trade balance.

³ CFA zone is used to express countries which have Franc CFA as currency.

2. Data and methodology

This study covers the period from 1996 to 2021 and concern all the eight countries under the West African and Monetary Union (WAEMU). This timeframe selected coincides with the current WAEMU common market which came into effect in 1996. The variables used in this study are Trade Balance, Real Exchange Rate Misalignment, trade openness, foreign direct investment, interest rate, and inflation rate sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI) database, publication of the world bank (2021) and Brugel dataset (2021). The relationship among the variables is modeled as follows:

$$TB = f (RERM, OPN, FDI, INT, INF) \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, the econometric model of the aforementioned model is given as:

$$TB_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RERM_{it} + \beta_2 OPN_{it} + \beta_3 FDI_{it} + \beta_4 INT_{it} + \beta_5 INF_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- TB is the Trade Balance. It is obtained by the ratio of exports of goods and services (X) to imports of goods and services (M) of the country (X/M). The foregoing is widely used in the empirical investigation of trade balance and some variables of interest (see Bahmani-Oskooee & Brook, 1999; Yeshineh, 2017; Naze, 2018; Mamun et al., 2021).
- RERM is the Exchange Rate Misalignment. This is the variable of interest for the study. It has been obtained by decomposition of Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER) using Hodrick Prescott Filter. The output gives the fitted values e.i the equilibrium real exchange rate values (EREER_{it}) and the corresponding misalignments is obtained by subtracting the equilibrium value from the actual value (RERM_{it} = REER_{it} – EREER_{it}) for each year (t) and for each country (i). Given that the currency (FCFA) is in a specified quotation (range), for instance, if RERM_{it} < 0, the currency is undervalued and if RERM_{it} > 0, the currency is overvalued and if RERM_{it} = 0, the FCFA is aligned. According to the theory, the real exchange rate misalignment is expected to impact negatively trade balance.
- OPN is the Trade Openness. It measures the degree to which trade barriers are eased. It is expressed as the reduction of trade obstacles that impede the movement of goods and services between nations. The ratio of exports and imports of goods and services to GDP is used to calculate trade openness. The use of this variable is consistent with Ghani (2009), Chaudhary and Amin

(2012), Hounson and Ayivodji (2020) and Nga (2020). It can impact positively or negatively trade balance. So, it has an ambiguous sign of coefficient.

- FDI is the Foreign Direct Investment. It is an investment carried out by an enterprise or company that is either whole or partly foreign-owned. It is the summed aggregate of the inflow of foreign direct investment into the sampled countries during the period under review. It has been used according to the studies of Nga (2020), Sharif and Ali (2016), Mohammad (2010), and Liu et al. (2001). It is expected to influence positively the trade balance.
- INT is the Interest Rate. It is the rate at which deposit money banks lend or grant money to industries, businesses, and the general public. It is also quantified as the interest rate charged by banks on consumer loans. This is in conformity with the works of Bahmani-Oskooee (1992), Mensah et al. (2016), Okoye et al. (2015), etc. It is expected to influence negatively the trade balance.
- INF is the Inflation Rate. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) is used as a proxy for inflation. The CPI measures the yearly percentage change in the cost of obtaining a basket of goods and services for the average consumer. Sharif and Ali (2016), Ousseini et al. (2017), and Okoye et al. (2015) used this inflation metric. It is expected to be negative.
- μ = Error term or white noise; i = sampled countries; t = Time period and $\beta_0 - \beta_5$ = Intercept and coefficients of the estimated parameters.

To estimate Equation (2), we have to check the stationarity and the cointegration of the variables. To realize the foregoing, we implement the panel unit root test proposed by Levin, Lin and Chu (2002), and Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003). To test whether the cointegration relationship exists in the estimated equations, we employed Pedroni (2004) and Johansen Fisher (1998) tests.

Finally, the model is estimated by using Mean Group Estimator (MGE) and Pooled Mean Group Estimator (PMGE) model known as panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag models (panel ARDL). These models are in error correction form and produces simultaneously both short-run and long-run effects from the panel dataset with a large cross-section and time-series. The advantage is that they (MGE and PMGE) can be applied irrespective of whether the variables exert different orders of integration (i.e. $I(0)$ or $I(1)$). However, to check whether there is a significant difference between the PMGE and the MGE, a Hausman (1978) test is conducted. At the end, post-estimation and panel causality tests were conducted.

Equation (2) transformed to Autoregressive Distributed lag (ARDL) approach developed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001), is stated as:

$$Y_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^p \tau_{ij} Y_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \delta_{ij} X_{it-j} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

where the number of groups $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$; the number of periods $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$; Y_{it} is the dependent variable, X_{it} is a $k \times 1$ vector of explanatory variables, δ_{ij} are the $k \times 1$ coefficient vectors; τ_{ij} are scalars; and μ_i is the group-specific effect. T must be large enough such that the model can be fitted for each group separately. Time trends and other fixed regressors may be included.

If the variables in (2) are, for example, $I(1)$ and cointegrated, then the error term is an $I(0)$ process for all i . A principal feature of cointegrated variables is their responsiveness to any deviation from long-run equilibrium. This feature implies an error correction model in which the short-run dynamics of the variables in the system are influenced by the deviation from equilibrium. Thus, it is common to reparametrize (2) into the error correction equation.

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \phi_i (y_{i,t-1} - \theta_i X_{it}) + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \tau_{ij} \Delta y_{it-1} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \delta_{ij} \Delta X_{it-j} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

The parameter ϕ_i is the error-correcting speed of adjustment term. If $\phi_i = 0$, then there would be no evidence for a long-run relationship. This parameter is expected to be significantly negative under the prior assumption that the variables show a return to a long-run equilibrium of particular importance is the vector θ_i , which contains the long-run relationships between the variables.

3. Results and Discussions

This section presents and discuss the results of the descriptive and inferential statistics generated from the analysis. The results of the descriptive analysis are reported in Table 1. This indicates that there are 208 observations per variable. Only RERM has a negative mean, meaning that there is a persistent period and size of undervaluation compared to overvaluation. Note that the mean of trade balance is 0.69 implying that the ratio of exports to imports during the sample period was an average of about 69 percent. It means also that exports are less than imports, therefore the countries under study recorded a deficit trade balance to the tune of about 31 percent i.e., (69 - 100).

Table 1 : Summary Statistics of the Variables used for the Estimation

Statistics	TB	RERM	OPN	FDI	INT	INF
Mean	0.687150	-2.53E-13	0.493044	2.060849	5.614382	2.634282
Maximum	1.277920	9.697751	0.988070	18.81778	10.79417	50.73405
Minimum	0.310548	-15.00923	0.133526	-	4.520000	-3.502586
Std. Dev.	0.210051	3.351576	0.152546	2.313912	0.979073	5.348714
Observations	208	208	208	208	208	208
Source: Author's computation using Eviews Version 10, 2024						

The inferential analysis, starts with unit root tests using the Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) and Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) tests. The results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Panel Unit Root Tests

Time series	LLC				IPS			
	t at level	Prob	t at F-D	Prob	t at level	Prob	t at F-D	Prob
TB	1.17	0.879	-2.32**	0.010	0.37	0.355	-6.11***	0.000
RERM	-5.52***	0.000	-10.15***	0.000	-4.22***	0.000	-10.12***	0.000
OPN	2.13	0.984	-7.17***	0.000	2.06	0.981	-2.50***	0.006
FDI	0.61	0.728	-3.39***	0.000	-0.29	0.385	-7.89***	0.000
INT	-6.47***	0.000	-10.82***	0.000	-3.73***	0.000	-9.94***	0.000
INF	-12.16***	0.000	-12.91***	0.000	-11.28***	0.000	-16.20***	0.000

Source computed by the author using Eviews version 10, 2024

Note: *** and **significant at 1% and 5% respectively; t is t-statistic; F-D is the first difference.

From the results reported in Table 2 real exchange rate misalignment, interest rate and inflation rate are stationary at level value on both LLC and IPS tests at 1% level of significance. According to the same results, the other variables which are trade balance, openness and foreign direct investment are stationary only at first difference on both LLC and IPS tests. The panel unit root tests confirmed that, the variables are stationary at different order of integrations. To avoid the problem of spurious results, this study applied Pooled Mean Group Estimator (PMGE) and Mean Group Estimator (MGE) because these approaches provide valid and reliable results irrespective of whether the panel dataset is stationary at level $I(0)$ or at first difference $I(1)$.

The cointegration tests presented in table 3 and table 4 in below, reveal evidence of long run relation between trade balance and the explanatory variables.

Table 3: Pedroni Panel Cointegration Test

Test	Statistics	P-value
Within-Dimension		
Panel v-Statistic	-1.504268	0.9337
Panel rho-Statistic	0.186630	0.5740
Panel PP-Statistic	-2.257476	0.0120**
Panel ADF-Statistic	-1.835708	0.0332**
Between-Dimension		
Group rho-Statistic	1.282706	0.9002
Group PP-Statistic	-5.149783	0.0000***
Group ADF-Statistic	-2.338165	0.0097***
Note: *** and ** significant at 1% and 5% respectively.		

Source: Author's computation from Eviews version 10, 2024

Indeed, the results of Pedroni test suggest that there is evidence of cointegration among the variables according to Panel PP-statistic, Panel ADF-statistic, Group PP-statistic and Group ADF-statistic tests. Although some tests such as Panel v-Statistic, Panel rho-Statistic and Group rho-Statistics are not statistically significant. In spite of that, the null hypothesis of no cointegration cannot be accepted for these tests. But according to Pedroni (2004) the panel ADF and group ADF tests have better small sample properties than the other tests; hence their test results are statistically significant at 5% and 1% level respectively.

Table 4 provides the results of Johansen Fisher cointegration tests called trace test and Eigen-value test. From the trace test, when $r \leq 2$ at 1% the null hypothesis is rejected because the probability is less than 1%. Therefore, the alternative one is accepted, that is $r = 3$. Also, when $r \leq 3$, at 1% the null hypothesis can be rejected meaning that there are no more than 3 cointegration relations between the variables. On the other hand, the same conclusion is valid for the Eigen-value test at 5%. Thus, accordingly, there exists a long-run relationship among the variables of the model. These results support the Pedroni test results of cointegration. Therefore, we conclude that the variables are cointegrated.

Table 4: Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration (trace and Eigen Value tests)

H0	Ha	Trace statistic	Prob.	Max-eigen value	Prob.
$r \leq 0$	$r = 1$	155.3	0.0000***	98.39	0.0000***
$r \leq 1$	$r = 2$	74.51	0.0000***	49.44	0.0000***
$r \leq 2$	$r = 3$	35.79	0.0031***	27.96	0.0320**
$r \leq 3$	$r = 4$	19.26	0.2554	12.97	0.6751
$r \leq 4$	$r = 5$	15.65	0.4777	11.37	0.7859
$r \leq 5$	$r = 6$	26.32	0.0496**	26.32	0.0496**

Note: *** and ** significant at 1% and 5% respectively.

H₀: there are no more than r cointegration relations and Ha alternative hypothesis.

Source: Author's computation from Eviews version 10, 2024

Given the existence of long run relationship among the variables and due the fact that these variables are integrated in different orders, the long and short run coefficients of the variables are estimated using PMGE and MGE. The results are presented in table 5.

Table 5: Results for PMGE, MGE, Hausman and Normality tests

dependent variable: Trade Balance (TB)						
Variable	PMGE			MGE		
	Coefficients	t-statistic	Prob.	coefficients	t-statistic	Prob.
Long-run coefficients						
RERM	-0.013***	-3.897	0.000	-0.016*	-1.830	0.067
OPN	0.272**	2.488	0.014	0.511	0.630	0.532
FDI	-0.063***	-3.779	0.000	-0.033	-1.440	0.149
INT	0.021	0.991	0.323	0.049**	2.450	0.014
INF	-0.007**	-2.196	0.030	-0.005	-0.360	0.717
Short-run coefficients						
ECM.	-0.266*	-1.907	0.059	-0.563***	-4.060	0.000
Δ RERM	0.003	0.712	0.478	0.005	1.050	0.296
Δ OPN	0.452**	2.565	0.011	0.437	1.640	0.102
Δ FDI	-0.002	-0.838	0.403	0.000	-0.040	0.968
Δ INT	-0.005*	-1.765	0.080	-0.012*	-1.950	0.051
Δ INF	0.001	0.927	0.355	-0.002	-0.550	0.585
Intercept	0.189	1.598	0.112	0.344***	2.810	0.005
Hausman test		2.660	0.752			
Normality test		12.678***	0.002			

Note: ***, **, * significant at 1% 5% and 10% respectively

Source: Author's computation from Stata version 14, 2024

The Hausman test was employed in this investigation to identify the best estimator. We reject the null hypothesis, which indicates that there is no systematic difference between the MGE and PMGE coefficients, if the test's probability value for the chi-square coefficient of the Hausman test is less than 5%. Since PMGE will be inconsistent under the alternative hypothesis, Mean Group Estimator (MGE) will be the most suitable choice. If not, the Pooled Mean Group Estimator (PMGE) would be a more suitable method. The probability value (0.7518) is larger than 5%, according to the Hausman test results shown in Table 5. This suggests that the more appropriate, reliable, and efficient method is the Pooled Mean Group Estimator, therefore, the results of this test will be taken into account and will be interpreted. Error Correction Model (ECM) appears to have the right sign, according to Table 5, data as well. It is statistically significant at the 10% (0.059) level, negative, and less than one (-0.266). This suggests that the estimate is relevant and verifies that there is a cointegration (long-term link) between the variables. The results also imply that in the case of any distortion in the economy, the system may correct itself at the speed of 26.6% every year. This speediness of correction is not surprising in Africa particularly in WAEMU countries where the adjustment policies are inadequate and slowly. Hence, all things being equal, it takes the economy approximately three (3) years and nine (9) months ($1/0.266$) to restore back to equilibrium in case of shocks. Also, the Jarque-Bera Normality test implies that the data does not follow a normal distribution. Nevertheless, according to Central Limit Theorem the non-normal distribution of the data does not affect the quality of the findings because of the sample size which has 806 so, more than one hundred (100) observations.

However, in the long run, the results reveal that real exchange rate misalignment has a significant negative effect on trade balance even at 1% level. Any increase (decrease) of RERM of one unit will decrease (increase) the trade balance in average of 0.013 unit in the union. It means that the RERM has the expected effect and it is in line with the findings of Mamun et al. (2021), Rikhotso and Bonga-Bonga (2021), Abbas et al. (2020), Njindan (2016), Ibrahim (2016), Nicita (2013) and Fuat (1998), among other. Concerning trade openness, the results advocate that it has a significant positive influence on trade balance at 5% level. It reveals that Any 1-unit rise in trade openness affects about 0.27 units growth in the trade balance in the sampled African countries. Further, the finding is in line with the results of Ghani (2009), Akintoye (2013), Mushtaq et al. (2014), Hounsou and Ayivodji (2020), who found a positive significant effect of trade openness on trade balance. Looking at foreign direct investment, the results show that, a significant negative influence on trade

balance at 1% level. When the inflows of foreign direct investment increase or decrease by 1%, the trade balance in the target union will decrease or increase by 0.063% over the study period. This finding is similar to those of Nga (2020), Sharif and Ali (2016), and Keho (2020). Additionally, it is evident from the data that, at a 5% level, the inflation rate has a long-term, substantial impact on the trade balance. This implies even further that, over the course of the study period, the sampled WEAMU countries' trade balance is negatively impacted by the long-term inflation rate. The findings suggest that variations in the inflation rate are associated with variations in the trade balance within the study region. A 1% rise or fall in the inflation rate will result in a 0.007% damage or improvement to the trade balance. The findings are aligned with works of Okoye et al. (2015), Hounsou and Ayivodji (2020), who found a significant negative effect of inflation rate on trade balance. The results contradict also the finding of Sharif and Ali (2016) who state that inflation rate has no impact on trade balance. The negative effect of inflation rate on trade balance in the countries under study is not surprising. It can be justified by the fact that in these countries, inflation is a source of welfare for the traders who borrow to import more and consequently, trade balance will be deteriorated. The remain of the variables has no significant effect on trade balance in the long run.

In the short term, the result demonstrates that at 5% level of significance, trade openness significantly improves trade balance. The trade balance increases by roughly 0.45 units for every unit rise in trade openness. The results also imply that during the study period, trade openness improves trade balance in the long and short terms in WAEMU countries. In a similar vein, the findings reveal that, at a 10% level, interest rates have a substantial negative impact on trade balance. For example, a 1% increase or decrease in interest rates will result in a 0.005% drop or gain in the trade balance. Nevertheless, the results contradict Mensah et al. (2016) and Okoye et al. (2015) findings who reported a positive significant effect of interest rate on trade balance in their studies. The remain of the variables has no significant effect on trade balance in the short run.

Conclusion

Based on the results, this study concludes that real exchange rate misalignment, foreign direct investment, interest rate and inflation rate have a significant negative effect on trade balance, while trade openness has a significant positive effect. The study further concludes that real exchange rate misalignment effect is minimal and appears on trade balance only at the long term. In line of these findings, this study recommends the need for WAEMU countries to focus attention on enhancing

the quality and innovation of their export products to sustain trade surplus. To do so, there is the need for primary raw materials to be transformed before export. In addition, they would expand into new and emerging markets to capitalize on the benefits of their undervalued currency. This is due to the fact that African countries need to orient their economies towards export diversification. Alternatively, WAEMU should consider adopting a flexible exchange rate regime to reduce the persistence of CFA franc misalignment. Also, the countries under study must still play on investment Code (good investment climate) by for instance accelerating the public-private partnership (PPP); improving the domestic investment and orients the inflows of foreign direct investment to industrial sector. In addition, reduction of lending rate will serve as one of the simple ways for the industry not only to get easy access to loan or capital but also to have a good rate of return on investment which together will motivate them to produce. Therefore, exports will increase and imports will decrease due to fact that availability of substitute goods and services. This policy will boost domestic consumption and investment and consequently enhance trade balance.

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